

Supplementary data

Suppl. F1. Data processing flow-chart.

Suppl. F2. Net change within each class in the Northwestern Coastline of Guinea-Bissau from 2000 to 2020. The net change for each class was calculated by subtracting the gains from losses based on results of Figure 2.

Suppl. F3. Contribution to net change experienced by coastal LULC in the northwestern coastline of Guinea-Bissau from 2000-2020.

Supp. F4. Net change within each class in the northwestern coastline of Guinea-Bissau from 2040 to 2060.

Supp. F5. Gains and losses by each class between 2040 and 2060 in the northwestern coastline of Guinea-Bissau.

Suppl. F6. The increase and decrease dynamic of coastal LULC from 2000-2060 in the study area.

Suppl. F7. Total net gains and losses of the four main LULC from 2000-2060 in the northwestern coastline of Guinea-Bissau.

Suppl. F8. Sea-level projection values without coastal protection in the study area from 2020 to 2080 based on local data and RCP8.5 scenarios.

Suppl. T1

SLAMM category and code.

N.	Coastal LULC classes	SLAMM category	SLAMM code
1	Mangrove	Mangrove	9
2	Developed land	Developed dry land	1
3	Mixed forest	Irregularly flooded forest	26
4	Tidal flat	Regularly flooded marsh	11
5	Sand Beach	Ocean beach	12
6	Open water	Ocean flat	13

Suppl. T2

Contribution to net change experienced by coastal LULC in the northwestern coastline of Guinea-Bissau from 2040-2080.

LULC	Contribution to Net change in Km ² from 2040 to 2060					
	Mangrove	Developed land	Mixed forest	Tidal flat	Sand beach	Open water
Mangrove	0.00	0.10	0.21	-1.90	0.17	0.24
Developed land	-0.10	0.00	11.14	4.53	-0.15	-0.05
Mixed forest	-0.21	-11.14	0.00	0.08	-0.05	-0.00
Tidal flat	1.90	-4.53	-0.08	0.00	0.09	-20.00
Sand beach	-0.24	0.15	0.05	-0.09	0.00	0.04
Open water	-0.24	0.05	0.00	20.00	-0.04	0.00

Suppl. T3

Contribution to net change experienced by coastal LULC in the northwestern coastline of Guinea-Bissau from 2040-2080.

LULC	Contribution to Net change in Km ² from 2040 to 2060					
	Mangrove	Developed land	Mixed forest	Tidal flat	Sand beach	Open water
Mangrove	0.00	0.10	0.21	-1.90	0.17	0.24
Developed land	-0.10	0.00	11.14	4.53	-0.15	-0.05
Mixed forest	-0.21	-11.14	0.00	0.08	-0.05	-0.00
Tidal flat	1.90	-4.53	-0.08	0.00	0.09	-20.00
Sand beach	-0.24	0.15	0.05	-0.09	0.00	0.04
Open water	-0.24	0.05	0.00	20.00	-0.04	0.00